

ON THE LEAST PRIMITIVE ROOT EXPRESSIBLE AS A SUM OF TWO SQUARES

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Abstract

For a positive integer n , a λ -root modulo n is an integer q coprime to n which has maximal order in $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$. We establish upper bounds for $s^*(n)$, the least λ -root modulo n which is expressible as a sum of two squares, in particular proving that for $\varepsilon > 0$, and n large enough there always exists a λ -root q modulo n in the range $1 \leq q \leq n^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}$ such that q is a sum of two squares.

1. Introduction and Statement

According to a folklore conjecture, all but finitely many primes p admit a positive *prime* primitive root q modulo p which is smaller than p , a problem that has not been resolved yet. Writing $g^*(p)$ for the least prime primitive root q , Martin [3] showed $g^*(p) \ll (\log p)^{B(\varepsilon)}$ for all but $O(Y^\varepsilon)$ primes $p \leq Y$, and Shoup [6] proved $g^*(p) \ll (\log p)^6$ for all p , conditionally on GRH (his result is stated for primitive roots, but it holds for prime primitive roots, too). Further information on this topic, and related problems is provided in [5].

In this paper we are interested in unconditional results valid for all primes, and therefore weaken the condition that the primitive root be a prime. Instead, as a natural variation, we ask for the smallest primitive root expressible as a sum of two squares. From a sieve-theoretic point of view this may be regarded as half way towards prime primitive roots. As it amounts to no extra effort, we treat the case of arbitrary moduli n . Of course, $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ may not have a primitive root in general. Therefore we define a λ -root modulo n to be an integer coprime to n of maximal order in $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$. We write $s^*(n)$ for the smallest λ -root modulo n expressible as a sum of two squares, and prove the following unconditional result.

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Theorem 1. *For a positive integer n let n_c denote the largest odd cube-free divisor of n . Then, for any $\varepsilon > 0$ we have*

$$s^*(n) \ll_{\varepsilon} n_c^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon}.$$

The proof of Theorem 1 uses ideas of Martin [4] who treated the case of almost-primitive roots. It is based on a semi-linear lower bound sieve and Burgess' bound for short character sums. The semi-linear sieve is applicable because primes represented by $x^2 + y^2$ have density $1/2$ in the set of all primes. We thus note that, as a generalization of Theorem 1, our method also works if one considers λ -roots represented by any binary quadratic form of class number 1.

The necessary notations and results from sieve theory will be provided in Section 2. In Section 3 we develop a sieve setting appropriate to our problem and note some preliminary results which are needed in the sequel. Finally, in Section 4 we proceed with the proof of Theorem 1.

Throughout this paper, \mathbb{N} shall denote the set of positive integers. For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $\varphi(n)$ the order, and by $\lambda(n)$ the exponent of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$. By $\text{rad}(n)$, and $\omega(n)$ we mean the largest squarefree divisor, and the number of distinct prime divisors of n , respectively.

2. The Semi-Linear Sieve

As usual in sieve theory we denote by \mathcal{A} a set of positive integers, and for any $d \in \mathbb{N}$ we let $\mathcal{A}_d := \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid a \equiv 0 \pmod{d}\}$. For a set \mathcal{P} of rational primes, and a positive parameter z we let $\mathcal{P}(z)$ be the product of all primes $p \in \mathcal{P}$ smaller than z . The predominant goal in sieve theory consist of estimating the quantity

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z) := \#\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid (a, \mathcal{P}(z)) = 1\}.$$

To this end one assumes that for any $d \in \mathbb{N}$ one has an asymptotic formula

$$\#\mathcal{A}_d = g(d)X + r_d \tag{1}$$

for the size of \mathcal{A}_d . Here the so called density function $g(d)$ is a multiplicative function, and X is a real parameter which serves as an approximation to the size of \mathcal{A} . The remainder terms r_d are intended to be rather small (at least on average over d). In a probabilistic sense one may then expect that X multiplied with

$$V(z) := \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{P} \\ p < z}} (1 - g(p))$$

yields a good approximation for $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z)$. This is indeed true under appropriate assumptions, and we state the following result which is a special case of a beta sieve

of sieve dimension $\kappa = \frac{1}{2}$ (cf. [2, p.207,275]). Since we are merely interested in lower bounds for $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z)$ we omit the upper bound version.

Theorem 2. *Assume that the function $g(d)$ in (1) satisfies*

$$\prod_{\substack{w \leq p < z \\ p \in \mathcal{P}}} (1 - g(p))^{-1} \leq \left(\frac{\log z}{\log w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{L}{\log w} \right) \tag{2}$$

for all $2 \leq w \leq z$, with some constant $L \geq 1$. Then, for $s \geq 1$ we have

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z) \geq XV(z) \left\{ f(s) + O\left((\log D)^{-\frac{1}{6}} \right) \right\} + O\left(\sum_{\substack{d|\mathcal{P}(z) \\ d < D}} |r_d| \right), \tag{3}$$

where $s = \log D / \log z$, and the first implied constant depends on L . For $1 \leq s \leq 3$ the function $f(s)$ is given by

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{e^\gamma}{\pi s}} \log \left(1 + 2(s - 1) + 2\sqrt{s(s - 1)} \right)$$

with γ denoting the Euler-Mascheroni constant.

3. Description of the Method and Preliminary Results

We now translate our problem into an appropriate sieve setting in order to make Theorem 2 applicable. From now on, let n be a fixed positive integer, $x > 0$ a real parameter, and set

$$\mathcal{A} := \{1 \leq a < x \mid a \text{ is a } \lambda\text{-root modulo } n, a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}\}.$$

Furthermore \mathcal{P} will be the set of primes $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then we aim to bound

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z) := \#\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid (a, \mathcal{P}(z)) = 1\}$$

from below for a suitable choice of the parameters z and x . Indeed, if $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z) \geq 1$ for $z > \sqrt{x}$, there exists a λ -root modulo n less than x which is expressible as a sum of two squares, since an odd number in \mathcal{A} must have an even number of prime divisors in \mathcal{P} .

Before we can apply Theorem 2 to our problem, it is essential to derive an asymptotic formula for $\#\mathcal{A}_d$ as in (1). Therefore we let $\gamma(k)$ denote the characteristic function of λ -roots modulo n , i.e. $\gamma(k) = 1$, if k is a λ -root modulo n , and $\gamma(k) = 0$, otherwise. Since $\gamma(k)$ is periodic with period n , and with support inside the set of integers coprime to n , it admits a unique expression as a linear combination of Dirichlet characters modulo n . This linear combination has been determined in Lemma 4 and 5 of [4] which we summarize in the following lemma.

Lemma 3. *Let G be the subgroup of Dirichlet characters modulo n given by*

$$G = \left\{ \chi_{\frac{\lambda(n)}{\text{rad}(\lambda(n))}} \mid \chi \pmod{n} \right\}.$$

For every prime p dividing $\varphi(n)$, let $m(p)$ denote the number of independent characters of order p in G . For every character χ modulo n let $\sigma(\chi)$ denote its order. Then, for any integer k we have

$$\gamma(k) = \sum_{\chi(n)} c_\chi \chi(k),$$

where the coefficients c_χ are given by

$$c_\chi = \begin{cases} \prod_{p|\sigma(\chi)} \left(\frac{-1}{p^{m(p)}} \right) \prod_{\substack{p|\varphi(n) \\ p \nmid \sigma(\chi)}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{m(p)}} \right), & \text{if } \chi \in G, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and satisfy the equation

$$\sum_{\chi(n)} |c_\chi| = 2^{\omega(\varphi(n))} c_0,$$

where $c_0 := c_{\chi_0}$, and χ_0 is the principal character modulo n .

The error term in the asymptotic formula for $\sharp \mathcal{A}_d$, which we proceed to prove in the subsequent section, involves short sums of consecutive values of characters $\chi \in G$. To this end we state the following result (cf. Lemma 7 in [4]) which yields appropriate estimates for such sums, and is based on a more general result of Burgess (cf. [1]).

Lemma 4. *For every $G \ni \chi \neq \chi_0$, $M, N \geq 1$, and $0 < \eta < 1$ we have*

$$\sum_{M < k \leq M+N} \chi(k) \ll N \left(\frac{n_c^{1/4+\eta}}{N} \right)^\eta.$$

4. Proof of Theorem 1

We begin with the deduction of an asymptotic formula for $\sharp \mathcal{A}_d$.

Lemma 5. *For a positive integer $d \leq x$ we have*

$$\sharp \mathcal{A}_d = g(d)X + r_d, \tag{4}$$

where $X := \frac{c_0 x \varphi(2n)}{4n}$ with c_0 as in Lemma 3, and $g(d)$ is a multiplicative function given by

$$g(d) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } (d, 2n) > 1, \\ \frac{1}{d}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For any $0 < \eta \leq 1$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and $D \leq x$ the remainder terms r_d satisfy

$$\sum_{\substack{d|\mathcal{P}(z) \\ d < D}} |r_d| \ll_{\varepsilon, \eta} X n_c^\varepsilon \left(\frac{n_c^{1/4+\eta}}{x} \right)^\eta D^\eta.$$

Proof. If $(d, n) > 1$ or $2 \mid d$ we clearly have $\mathcal{A}_d = \emptyset$. For d odd and $(d, n) = 1$ we deduce by Lemma 3

$$\begin{aligned} \#\mathcal{A}_d &= \sum_{\substack{k \leq x \\ k \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ k \equiv 0 \pmod{d}}} \gamma(k) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ kd \equiv 1 \pmod{4}}} \sum_{\chi \in G} c_\chi \chi(kd) \\ &= c_0 \chi_0(d) \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ k \equiv d \pmod{4}}} \chi_0(k) + \sum_{\substack{\chi \in G \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} c_\chi \chi(d) \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ k \equiv d \pmod{4}}} \chi(k). \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By Möbius inversion the first sum in (5) equals

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ k \equiv d \pmod{4} \\ (k, n) = 1}} 1 &= \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ k \equiv d \pmod{4}}} \sum_{\substack{f|k \\ f|n}} \mu(f) \\ &= \sum_{f|n} \mu(f) \sum_{\substack{l f \leq x/d \\ l f \equiv d \pmod{4}}} 1 \\ &= \frac{x}{4d} \sum_{\substack{f|n \\ 2 \nmid f}} \frac{\mu(f)}{f} + O\left(2^{\omega(n)}\right) \\ &= \frac{x}{4d} \frac{\varphi(2n)}{n} + O\left(2^{\omega(n)}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The second sum in (5) can be estimated using Lemma 3 and 4. If $d_0 \equiv d \pmod{4}$ with $d_0 \in \{1, 3\}$, and m is an integer satisfying $4m \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{\chi \in G \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} c_\chi \chi(d) \sum_{\substack{k \leq x/d \\ k \equiv d \pmod{4}}} \chi(k) &\ll \sum_{\substack{\chi \in G \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} |c_\chi| \left| \chi(m) \sum_{0 \leq l \leq \frac{x}{4d} - \frac{d_0}{4}} \chi(4l + d_0) \right| \\ &\ll \sum_{\substack{\chi \in G \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} |c_\chi| \left| \sum_{0 \leq l \leq \frac{x}{4d} - \frac{d_0}{4}} \chi(l + md_0) \right| \\ &\ll c_0 2^{\omega(\varphi(n))} \frac{x}{d} \left(\frac{d}{x} n_c^{1/4+\eta} \right)^\eta. \end{aligned}$$

By (5) and (6) the remainder term r_d is therefore

$$\ll c_0 2^{\omega(n)} + c_0 2^{\omega(\varphi(n))} \frac{x}{d} \left(\frac{d}{x} n_c^{1/4+\eta} \right)^\eta \ll_\varepsilon \frac{1}{d} \frac{c_0 x \varphi(2n)}{4n} n_c^\varepsilon \left(\frac{d}{x} n_c^{1/4+\eta} \right)^\eta,$$

since $d \leq x$ and $\eta \leq 1$. Using the definition of X , we finally deduce

$$\sum_{\substack{d|\mathcal{P}(z) \\ d < D}} |r_d| \leq \sum_{d < D} |r_d| \ll_\varepsilon X n_c^\varepsilon \left(\frac{n_c^{1/4+\eta}}{x} \right)^\eta \sum_{d < D} d^{\eta-1} \ll_\eta X n_c^\varepsilon \left(\frac{n_c^{1/4+\eta}}{x} \right)^\eta D^\eta.$$

□

Using Theorem 2, and the preceding lemma we may now prove the following modified version of Theorem 1.

Theorem 6. *For a positive integer n , and x a positive real parameter, let $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A})$ denote the number of odd λ -roots q modulo n in the range $0 < q < x$, such that q is expressible as a sum of two squares, and set $X := \frac{c_0 x \varphi(2n)}{4n}$. Then, for any $0 < \eta < \frac{1}{2}$ there exists $x_0(\eta) \geq 1$ such that*

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}) \gg_\eta \frac{X}{\sqrt{\log x}}$$

holds, whenever $x > \max\{x_0(\eta), n_c^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{5\eta}{1-2\eta}}\}$.

Proof. Inserting the multiplicative function $g(d)$ from Lemma 5 into the definition of $V(z)$ one can easily verify that (2) is satisfied, and $V(z) \sim \frac{c_n}{\sqrt{\log z}}$ holds with some constant $c_n \geq 1$ depending on n (cf. [2, p.277f]). Hence Theorem 2 is applicable. If $z > \sqrt{x}$, we clearly have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}) &\geq \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A}, z) \\ &\gg \frac{X}{\sqrt{\log x}} \left\{ f(s) + O\left((\log D)^{-\frac{1}{6}}\right) \right\} + O_{\eta,\varepsilon} \left(X n_c^\varepsilon \left(\frac{n_c^{1/4+\eta}}{x} \right)^\eta D^\eta \right) \end{aligned}$$

by Theorem 2 and Lemma 5. Now we define $D := \frac{x^{1-\eta}}{n_c^{2\eta+1/4}}$, and set $\varepsilon = \eta^2$. With these choices the above error term becomes $o(X/\sqrt{\log x})$. If we choose x according to the condition

$$x > n_c^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{5\eta}{1-2\eta}},$$

we obtain $D > x^{1/2}$, and hence $f(s) > 0$. This completes the proof. □

Finally, Theorem 1 is a simple consequence of the previous theorem. Indeed, for any $0 < \eta < \frac{1}{2}$ Theorem 6 implies that $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A})$ is positive, whenever

$$x > x_0(\eta) n_c^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{5\eta}{1-2\eta}}$$

is satisfied. Since $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{A})$ is a counting function, it must therefore be ≥ 1 , and Theorem 1 follows.

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